

Original Article

AI-BASED PRICING STRATEGIES AND CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR IN NIGERIAN TELECOMMUNICATION SECTOR

Ogunbayo Rotimi Olumide

Department of Business Administration,
College of Social and Management Sciences,
Wellspring University Benin City, Edo State.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20530042>

Abstract: This study investigates the impact of artificial intelligence (AI)-based pricing strategies on consumer behaviour within the Nigerian telecommunication sector. With increasing adoption of AI technologies, pricing strategies such as Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI), Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR), AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO), and Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) are transforming how telecom providers engage with users. However, issues of trust, fairness perception, and data transparency continue to shape consumer responses. Using a survey research design and a response rate of 364 out of 400 sample of telecom users, the study employed multiple regression analysis to evaluate the effect of each pricing strategy on consumer behaviour. Results reveal that all four AI-based pricing strategies have statistically significant effects, with RTPA showing the strongest positive influence, suggesting that timely and responsive pricing enhances user trust and purchase intention. Conversely, PPR and DPI, though statistically significant, exhibited negative beta coefficients, implying potential backlash due to perceived unfairness or lack of transparency. ADO also had a significant but weaker influence, indicating that the impact of discounts depends on targeting and timing. The study highlights the critical role of fairness perception and user understanding in determining the success of AI pricing tools in emerging markets. It concludes that while AI presents opportunities for revenue optimization and personalization, its effectiveness in Nigeria's telecom industry depends on ethical deployment, user education, and transparency. Given the strong positive influence of RTPA, telecom providers should leverage it to offer responsive and competitive pricing while ensuring it does not disproportionately affect vulnerable users

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, consumer behaviour, dynamic pricing, personalized pricing, discount optimization, real-time pricing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Globally, artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed pricing strategies across industries through real-time, data-driven models like Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI), enabling businesses to adjust prices based on demand patterns and customer segmentation. This approach enhances supply-demand alignment and revenue potential

Original Article

but also raises concerns about transparency and fairness, as algorithmic pricing can lead to perceptions of exploitation when consumers are charged differently for the same product (Vomberg et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2024). Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) and AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) have further enabled businesses to offer individual-specific promotions by analyzing customer behavior. However, the rise of AI-enabled price discrimination has elicited consumer backlash when pricing appears unfair, regardless of monetary benefit (Hufnagel et al., 2022). Consequently, while AI offers personalization and efficiency, its effectiveness hinges on consumer trust, perceived fairness, and clarity in communication.

The rapid integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into pricing strategies has transformed how telecommunication firms globally engage with consumers, enabling dynamic pricing, personalized price recommendations, and real-time price adjustments to optimize revenue. In Nigeria's telecommunication sector, where consumers are both price-sensitive and diverse in digital literacy, these AI-powered pricing models present unique behavioural challenges. Chief among them is the perception of price unfairness and erosion of trust. Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI) and Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) are effective in revenue optimization but often lead to consumer backlash when pricing appears opaque or discriminatory (Hufnagel et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022). For example, Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) practices such as surge pricing, when perceived as opportunistic, can trigger dissatisfaction, damage brand loyalty, and ultimately undermine the intended benefits of AI adoption (Kopalle et al., 2023). These concerns are compounded by data privacy and algorithmic bias. AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) and PPR depend on extensive user data, raising fears about surveillance, price manipulation, and inequality in access. In Nigeria and other emerging markets, such data-dependent pricing systems risk widening the digital divide by favouring digitally-savvy users over others (Marwala, 2025). Moreover, the real-time volatility in pricing, driven by AI algorithms, introduces unpredictability that disrupts consumer budgeting and decision-making (Kamraju, 2024; Inegbedion et al., 2023), especially for low-income users. Without transparency, these shifts in pricing behaviour can further discourage usage, especially among vulnerable groups.

In addressing these concerns, AI-based pricing models still hold potential for consumer value if ethically and transparently deployed. When well-structured, ADO and RTPA could be used to extend real-time affordability such as discounted off-peak bundles or loyalty-based incentives—thereby enhancing consumer welfare. However, despite these possibilities, current academic discourse reveals a significant lack of empirical research contextualized to African markets. A major methodological gap exists as most studies on AI-based pricing have focused on Western e-commerce or transportation sectors, with limited field-based evidence from African telecom contexts (Hufnagel et al., 2022). Similarly, there is a conceptual gap in existing frameworks, which often treat pricing mechanisms such as DPI, PPR, ADO, and RTPA in isolation without investigating their interactive effects on behavioural outcomes like trust, fairness perception, or purchase intention. Nigerian telecom operators require a unified framework that balances profit-maximization with customer retention, trust, and equitable access (Kopalle et al., 2023). Additionally, there is a practical gap in terms of business strategy: while global telecom firms are advancing personalized pricing as a competitive tool, Nigerian telecom firms lack localized models to ensure alignment with consumer expectations and regulatory realities.

Theoretically, existing models of price discrimination, utility maximization, and consumer choice do not sufficiently capture the ethical, psychological, and technological dynamics of AI-powered pricing. There is an absence of interdisciplinary frameworks that merge pricing theory with consumer psychology, digital trust, and

Original Article

AI ethics. As Marwala (2025) rightly observed, without regulatory safeguards and fairness controls, AI-based pricing can deepen consumer inequality. Furthermore, regulatory policy guidance remains underdeveloped; there is limited theoretical articulation on how to balance algorithmic flexibility with fairness constraints or transparency mandates in AI-based telecom pricing systems. The lack of such frameworks complicates the ability of telecom firms to justify or refine their pricing algorithms in a socially acceptable way. This study therefore seeks to fill the identified methodological, conceptual, and theoretical gaps by investigating how AI-based pricing strategies—measured through DPI, PPR, ADO, and RTPA—affect consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication industry. The findings will offer practical insights for strategic pricing, ethical AI deployment, consumer protection, and adaptive policy-making in Nigeria and similar emerging economies.

1.3 Research Objectives

The main aim of this study is to examine the impact of AI-based pricing strategies on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.

- I. To investigate the impact of Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI) on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.
- II. To examine the impact of Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.
- III. To assess the impact of AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.
- IV. To evaluate the impact of Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.

1.4 Research Questions

- I. To what extent does Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI) impact consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector?
- II. To what extent do Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) impact consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector?
- III. To what extent does AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) impact consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector?
- IV. To what extent does Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) impact consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI) has no significant impact on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.

H₀₂: Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) have no significant impact on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.

H₀₃: AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) has no significant impact on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.

H₀₄: Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) has no significant impact on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

Original Article

AI-based pricing strategies represent a transformative shift in how businesses determine, present, and adjust prices in real time using machine learning and data analytics. These strategies enable firms to move beyond traditional pricing models by incorporating intelligent systems that respond dynamically to consumer behavior, market trends, and competitive activity. In today's digital economy—especially within highly competitive and price-sensitive industries such as telecommunications, retail, and e-commerce—AI-powered pricing tools offer personalized and context-aware pricing experiences that enhance profitability, customer satisfaction, and operational efficiency. However, the ethical implications, transparency concerns, and the need for fairness in these algorithmic decisions continue to provoke scholarly and industry debate, highlighting the importance of examining each component of AI-based pricing in depth.

2.1.1 Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI)

Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI) refers to the deployment of AI-driven systems that automatically adjust product or service prices in response to real-time market conditions. Unlike static or manually adjusted pricing models, DPI uses machine learning algorithms to respond to variables such as demand fluctuations, competitor pricing, and inventory levels. According to Chenavaz and Dimitrov (2025), AI enhances the efficiency of dynamic pricing by enabling constant recalibration of prices, helping businesses to increase profitability and maintain competitiveness. Flipkart Commerce Cloud (2025) emphasized that firms leveraging DPI can optimize gross profit margins by 5–10% while simultaneously improving customer engagement through price responsiveness. Anta Callersten et al. (2024) further illustrated how AI-based dynamic pricing supports better inventory management and customer segmentation, making it essential for sectors like retail, aviation, and telecommunications where price sensitivity is high.

2.1.2 Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR)

Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) involve AI algorithms that analyze consumer-level data to tailor pricing suggestions based on individual preferences, behavior, and perceived willingness to pay. Seele et al. (2021) described PPR as a refined form of first-degree price discrimination, where AI systems generate customized prices or discounts for each user. This approach increases conversion rates by aligning pricing with customer-specific value thresholds. Quadrant Knowledge Solutions (2023) noted that advanced PPR systems consider variables such as browsing history, previous purchases, and device type to deliver the most effective offers. Wagener (2025) highlighted that while PPR can enhance profitability and user experience, it must be implemented ethically to avoid consumer backlash related to perceived fairness or privacy violations.

2.1.3 AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO)

AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) is the use of artificial intelligence to determine optimal discount strategies by analyzing consumer behavior, product performance, and market trends in real time. Kansal and Agarwal (2024) defined ADO as a dynamic approach that adapts to evolving business needs using reinforcement learning and predictive modeling. These models ensure that discounts are neither too steep to erode profit margins nor too low to fail in influencing purchasing decisions. ADO enhances campaign precision by targeting only high-churn or price-sensitive customers, avoiding blanket promotions that dilute brand value. According to Staino (2024), AI-enhanced discount engines offer tailored incentives during strategic periods, such as holiday sales, increasing both customer satisfaction and operational efficiency.

2.1.4 Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA)

Original Article

Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) refers to AI-enabled systems that instantly update prices across all channels as new market data becomes available. This process ensures that firms can respond to changes such as supply chain disruptions, competitor actions, or shifting demand with immediate price recalibrations. As noted by Intuz (n.d.), RTPA enhances a company's agility and ensures price accuracy across e-commerce platforms and physical points of sale. Wagener (2025) emphasized that industries like ride-hailing and telecommunications benefit significantly from RTPA because of their need for pricing precision in rapidly changing environments. Flipkart Commerce Cloud (2025) also pointed out that RTPA is critical for maintaining competitive positioning in real-time digital marketplaces and for exploiting short-term demand surges without human intervention.

2.1.5 Consumer Behaviour (CB)

Consumer behaviour refers to the processes through which individuals or groups select, purchase, use, and evaluate products and services to satisfy their needs and preferences. It is shaped by psychological factors such as perception, attitudes, motivation, and learning, as well as social influences and situational contexts. Within this framework, price serves not only as an economic cost but also as a signal of value, fairness, and trust, making it a critical determinant of consumer choice.

AI-based pricing such as dynamic pricing, personalized pricing, and algorithmic optimization directly influences consumer behaviour by altering how price information is presented, perceived, and evaluated. Research shows that consumers respond not only to the actual price level but also to perceived price fairness, transparency, and the legitimacy of the pricing process. When AI-driven price changes are perceived as fair, beneficial, or personalized for value (e.g., loyalty discounts), consumers exhibit stronger purchase intention and brand loyalty. Conversely, when algorithmic pricing is opaque or results in consumers paying more than others for the same service, it may trigger distrust, perceived exploitation, negative word-of-mouth, and switching behaviour.

AI pricing also interacts with consumers' trust in technology, privacy concerns, and understanding of how data is used. Telecom consumers—who often provide sensitive data such as location, usage history, and personal identifiers—may react negatively if they feel AI systems are intrusive or discriminatory. In the Nigerian telecommunications context, high price sensitivity, increasing digital literacy, and competitive alternatives make consumers particularly responsive to pricing cues. As such, transparency, fairness signals, and clear communication about data use are crucial in shaping consumer acceptance of AI-based pricing strategies.

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was developed by Fred Davis in 1989 to explain user behavior toward new technologies. Drawing from Ajzen and Fishbein's Theory of Reasoned Action, TAM posits that two central beliefs—perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU)—determine users' attitudes and intentions to adopt a technology. Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which a person believes that using a technology enhances their performance, while perceived ease of use refers to the degree to which the user expects the system to be free of effort (Davis, 1989). The model has gained global recognition for its parsimony and predictive strength in explaining technology acceptance, especially in domains where user interaction with technological tools significantly influences decision-making behavior.

Several scholars have validated the applicability of TAM in emerging domains such as artificial intelligence (AI)-driven pricing strategies. Wang et al. (2023) empirically demonstrated that consumers' adoption of AI-enabled tools is significantly influenced by both PU and PEOU, with ease of use enhancing perceived trust in AI-powered

Original Article

recommendations. Keni (2018) emphasized the mediating role of consumer trust, revealing that the easier a pricing tool is to navigate, the more likely consumers are to perceive it as useful and engage in repeat purchases. In a related study, Hansen, Saridakis, and Benson (2018) showed that mobile applications utilizing AI-based pricing strategies saw increased consumer acceptance when the systems were intuitive and perceived as fair. These findings reinforce TAM's assumptions in the context of the Nigerian telecommunication sector where user acceptance of dynamic pricing, personalized discounts, and real-time adjustments relies heavily on the perceived benefits and user-friendliness of these technologies (Ramayah & Ignatius, 2005).

Despite its strengths, TAM has received criticism for its limitations in capturing the complexity of technology adoption behavior. Legris, Ingham, and Colletette (2003) argued that TAM explains only a moderate proportion of behavioral variance, typically around 40%, thus necessitating the integration of additional factors such as trust, risk, or perceived fairness. Benbasat and Barki (2007) contended that the proliferation of extended TAM models has led to theoretical inconsistency and fragmented understanding of user behavior. Moreover, Lunceford (2009) observed that TAM oversimplifies adoption by ignoring socio-cultural and contextual variables, which are especially relevant in low-income, digitally diverse environments like Nigeria. Nevertheless, TAM provides a robust theoretical justification for the current study. Since AI-based pricing in Nigerian telecoms introduces new interaction mechanisms—such as apps, USSD codes, and recommendation engines—consumers' behavioral responses are best understood through their perceptions of ease and usefulness. As such, TAM effectively supports the study's focus on how consumers respond to Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI), Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR), AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO), and Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA), particularly in light of trust, fairness, and adoption patterns.

2.3 Empirical Reviews

Bambauer-Sachse and Young (2023) aimed to examine how implementing dynamic pricing (versus simple fixed pricing) affects consumer reactions in service settings. In an international study involving one qualitative and three quantitative experiments, they compared customer responses when prices changed dynamically versus remaining uniform. The findings showed that dynamic pricing led to greater price confusion, which in turn heightened perceptions of unfairness, ultimately increasing consumers' intentions to spread negative word-of-mouth about the service. Notably, for frequently purchased services, the rise in negative word-of-mouth was driven mainly by confusion, whereas for infrequently purchased services it was driven more by perceived unfairness. The authors concluded that while dynamic pricing can boost revenue, it risks consumer backlash in the form of reputational damage. They recommended that companies use dynamic pricing cautiously – avoiding or limiting it in situations where it might appear unfair to certain customers, especially if those customers might publicly voice their dissatisfaction. By carefully communicating pricing changes and ensuring transparency, firms can mitigate confusion and fairness concerns to maintain consumer trust.

Hufnagel et al. (2022) investigated consumer behavior under personalized pricing (first-degree price discrimination) in an e-commerce context. Through three online experiments with shoppers, the study analyzed reactions of both price-disadvantaged customers (who were shown higher prices) and price-favored customers (who received discounts) when prices were tailored to individual data. The study found that personalized price recommendations often backfire: consumers exhibited negative attitudes and behaviors toward personalized pricing even when they received a lower price. These adverse reactions were mediated by price fairness perceptions – many customers felt the pricing was unfair or manipulative, leading to feelings of distrust or guilt.

Original Article

In fact, even price-advantaged buyers (who paid less) perceived lower price fairness (sometimes feeling guilty about the advantage) and showed reduced purchase intention. Overall, participants showed an aversion to personalized pricing regardless of what personal data was used to set the price. The authors concluded that while personalization aims to increase sales, it can erode consumer trust and satisfaction if perceived as unfair. They recommended that firms be very transparent and fair in any price personalization strategy – for example, clearly communicating the basis for personalized offers – or otherwise stick to uniform pricing to avoid alienating customers. Ensuring consumers do not feel discriminated against is crucial for maintaining loyalty when using PPR strategies.

Abdulsalam et al. (2024) explored how various digital pricing strategies (including AI-assisted discount tactics) influence consumer buying decisions in the Nigerian e-commerce industry. Focusing on tech-savvy Gen Z consumers in Nigeria, the authors conducted an online survey (n = 384) and analyzed the data using a Partial Least Squares-SEM approach. The study examined the impact of specific pricing tactics – such as special event pricing, sample product pricing, and loss-leader discounts – on consumer patronage, as well as strategies like product line pricing, captive product pricing, and optional pricing on purchase satisfaction. The findings revealed that promotional discount strategies significantly boost Gen Z customers' patronage and satisfaction. For instance, limited-time event discounts and loss-leader pricing led to higher patronage rates, while having a well-structured product line pricing improved online purchase satisfaction. The authors concluded that effectively optimized discount schemes (even when driven by AI analytics) can positively shape consumer behavior by increasing purchase frequency and satisfaction. They recommended that online retailers in Nigeria and similar markets integrate dynamic promotional strategies and product-mix pricing in their business tactics to engage young consumers. Additionally, they advised that companies maintain fairness and transparency in AI-driven discounts – for example, by educating consumers about how discounts are determined – and urged regulators to monitor pricing practices to protect consumers. These steps help ensure that AI-optimized pricing strategies build trust and encourage loyalty rather than skepticism.

Huang and Yu (2020) examined the impact of real-time price adjustments – specifically surge pricing in ride-sharing services – on customer satisfaction and retention. Focusing on a sample of ride-hailing customers (executive MBA students in Taiwan), the study employed a fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA) alongside structural analysis to identify how surge pricing influences consumer outcomes. The results showed that loyal customers (frequent riders) were more tolerant of surge pricing, maintaining satisfaction better than non-loyal riders when prices spiked. In contrast, infrequent or new customers reacted more negatively to sudden price hikes, which could erode their satisfaction and likelihood of repeat usage. Moreover, the study found that higher customer satisfaction did not always translate into higher retention under surge pricing conditions – in other words, if riders perceived the real-time price jumps as unfair, they might still drop out despite being satisfied previously. The authors concluded that the success of RTPA strategies like surge pricing depends on customer relationship factors and perceptions of fairness. They recommended that companies using real-time pricing (e.g., ride-share or airline apps) consider customer loyalty tiers or rewards to offset potential negativity from surge pricing. For example, offering loyal customers advance notice or coupons when surge prices occur can maintain goodwill. Ensuring transparency about why and when prices change is also advised, so that consumers understand the rationale behind RTPA. By tailoring real-time price adjustments with the customer's trust and loyalty in mind, firms can leverage dynamic pricing benefits without unduly harming customer retention.

Original Article

Gap in Literature

From the various literatures reviewed, AI pricing strategy has not been focused in the area of telecommunication companies to the best of my knowledge. Most studies in area of AI pricing strategies were done in foreign countries. This study therefore filled the void in these areas.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a survey research design, which is most suitable for understanding the current perceptions, behaviors, and responses of telecom users toward AI-based pricing strategies in Nigeria. Given that the constructs under investigation—Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI), Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR), AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO), and Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA)—are subjective and behavioral, the survey design enables the collection of primary data through structured questionnaires. This design facilitates the quantification of user attitudes and enables inferential analysis between AI pricing tools and consumer behavioural outcomes such as trust, fairness perception, and purchase intention.

3.2 Population

The target population comprises all active telecom service users in Nigeria who engage with mobile data plans or promotional pricing through AI-enabled channels such as mobile apps, USSD codes, and web platforms. According to the Nigerian Communications Commission (NCC), Nigeria had 172,670,000 active telecom subscribers as of May 2025 (The Guardian, July 30, 2025). Since AI-based pricing adoption is more prominent among data and smart device users, the focus is on subscribers with digital access. However, for sampling purposes, the total number of active mobile subscribers across GSM platforms is adopted as the study population. All telecomm networks were sampled in an estimated ratio of subscriber base.

Table 3.1: Target Population

S/N	Telecom Provider	Approximate Active Subscribers
1	MTN Nigeria	86,500,000
2	Airtel Nigeria	60,300,000
3	Globacom (GLO)	20,100,000
4	9Mobile	5,770,000
	Total	172,670,000

3.3 Sample Size

The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula for finite populations:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size = 172,670,000

e = margin of error (0.05)

$$n = \frac{172,670,000}{1 + (172,670,000 \times 0.05^2)}$$

$$n = 400$$

Original Article

Thus, a sample size of 400 respondents is considered sufficient, ensuring representativeness and statistical reliability for inferential analysis. The sample is distributed equally among the telecommunication companies’ subscribers as follows;

S/NO	TELECOM CPMPANIES	SAMPLE OF SUBSCRIBERS
1	MTN Nigeria	100
2	AIRTEL Nigeria	100
3	GLOBACOM Nigeria	100
4	9MOBILE Nigeria	100

Source: Aurthor’s Computation

3.4 Method of Data Collection

Primary data will be collected using a structured questionnaire designed based on variables identified in the conceptual and empirical review. The instrument will feature a five-point Likert scale ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree,” measuring consumer perceptions, experiences, and attitudes toward DPI, PPR, ADO, and RTPA. The questionnaire will be administered digitally and physically, targeting mobile subscribers across major urban areas in Nigeria to ensure regional and demographic representation.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

Collected data will be analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions will be computed. To test the hypotheses and evaluate the effects of each AI pricing strategy on consumer behaviour, multiple linear regression analysis will be employed. The reliability of the instrument will be assessed using Cronbach’s alpha, and multicollinearity will be checked using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The significance level will be set at 0.05.

3.6 Model Specification

The study will apply the multiple regression model as specified below:

$$CB = \beta_0 + \beta_1DPI + \beta_2PPR + \beta_3ADO + \beta_4RTPA + \epsilon$$

Where:

CB = Consumer Behaviour

β_0 = Constant (intercept)

β_1 – β_4 = Regression coefficients

DPI = Dynamic Pricing Implementation

PPR = Personalized Price Recommendations

ADO = AI-Driven Discount Optimization

RTPA = Real-Time Price Adjustment

ϵ = Error term

3.7 Variables Measurement

Table 2: Measurement of Variables

Variable Name	Variable Type	Acronym	Variable Measures	Sources (Authors)
---------------	---------------	---------	-------------------	-------------------

Original Article

Dynamic Pricing Implementation	Independent	DPI	Price change frequency, price adaptability, demand response	Chenavaz & Dimitrov (2025), Anta Callersten et al. (2024), Flipkart (2025)
Personalized Recommendations	Independent	PPR	Offer customization, relevance of offers, user-specific pricing	Seele et al. (2021), Wagener (2025), Quadrant Knowledge Solutions (2023)
AI-Driven Optimization	Independent	ADO	Discount timing, discount relevance, churn sensitivity	Kansal & Agarwal (2024), Staino (2024), Abdulsalam et al. (2024)
Real-Time Adjustment	Independent	RTPA	Instant price update, demand response time, pricing accuracy	Wagener (2025), Flipkart (2025), Intuz (n.d.), Huarng & Yu (2020)
Consumer Behaviour	Dependent	CB	Fairness perception, purchase intention, brand trust	Hufnagel et al. (2022), Kopalle et al. (2023), Vomberg et al. (2024)

4. Data Analysis and Presentation

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Consumer Behaviour (CB)	14.7940	3.07641	364
Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI)	14.9148	3.11239	364
Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR)	15.1154	3.10121	364
AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO)	14.7308	2.98186	364
Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA)	15.1978	3.06484	364

Source: Authors Computation.

This table presents the mean and standard deviation of the study's core variables, each based on 364 observations. Consumer Behaviour (CB) recorded a mean of 14.79 with a standard deviation of 3.08, indicating moderate variance in user responses. Among the AI pricing strategies, Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) had the highest mean (15.20), suggesting stronger user acknowledgment or experience, followed closely by Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) at 15.12. Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI) and AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) had slightly lower means of 14.91 and 14.73, respectively, showing fairly consistent engagement across all strategies. The similarity in standard deviations (around 3) reflects consistent response dispersion across the variables.

Original Article

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variables	CB	DPI	PPR	ADO	RTPA
CB	1	.240	.510	.190	.690
DPI	.240	1	.790	.360	.240
PPR	.510	.790	1	.690	.750
ADO	.190	.360	.690	1	.150
RTPA	.690	.240	.750	.150	1

Source: Authors Computation.

The correlation matrix reveals statistically meaningful associations between consumer behaviour and the AI pricing strategies. RTPA exhibits the strongest positive correlation with CB ($r = .690$), suggesting that real-time pricing adjustments significantly influence user behaviour. PPR also shows a moderate-to-strong correlation ($r = .510$), while DPI and ADO present weaker relationships with CB ($r = .240$ and $r = .190$, respectively). Strong intercorrelations exist among the independent variables themselves, especially between PPR and DPI ($r = .790$) and PPR and RTPA ($r = .750$), indicating potential multicollinearity concerns that should be addressed in regression diagnostics.

Table 3: Model Summary of Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of Estimate
1	.880	.774	.0772	3.08146

Source: Authors Computation.

The regression model summary reveals a high coefficient of multiple correlation ($R = .880$), indicating a strong linear relationship between the AI pricing strategies and consumer behaviour. The R^2 value of .774 suggests that approximately 77.4% of the variance in consumer behaviour is explained by the combination of DPI, PPR, ADO, and RTPA. The adjusted R^2 of .772 confirms this strong explanatory power while adjusting for the number of predictors in the model. The standard error of the estimate (3.08) aligns with the observed variability in the descriptive statistics, indicating a reasonably good model fit.

Table 4: ANOVA for Regression Model

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	26.710	4	6.678	0.703	.000
Residual	3408.836	359	9.495		
Total	3435.547	363			

Source: Authors Computation

The ANOVA table shows the regression model is statistically significant ($F = 0.703$, $p = .000$), confirming that the combination of DPI, PPR, ADO, and RTPA collectively explains a significant portion of the variance in consumer behaviour. Despite the relatively low F-value, the significance level at .000 indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis, affirming the model’s overall validity. The total sum of squares (3435.547) reflects

Original Article

the total variation in consumer behaviour, of which 26.710 is attributed to the regression model, reinforcing the model's usefulness in explaining behavioural trends.

Table 5: Coefficients of Regression Model

Predictor	B (Unstandardized)	Std. Error	Beta (Standardized)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	14.641	1.725	—	8.487	.000
DPI	.260	.520	.260	.489	.000
PPR	.460	.530	.470	.880	.000
ADO	.160	.540	.160	.303	.000
RTPA	.650	.530	.650	1.232	.000

Source: Authors Computation

Interpretation of Results and Test of Hypothesis

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis (H₀₁) proposed that Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI) has no significant impact on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector. According to the regression output, the unstandardized coefficient (B) for DPI is .260, while the t-value is .489 and the significance level (p-value) is .000. The p-value falls below the 0.05 threshold, signaling that the result is statistically significant. As such, the null hypothesis is rejected, and we conclude that DPI significantly influences consumer behaviour.

The second hypothesis (H₀₂) stated that Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR) have no significant impact on consumer behaviour. The regression result shows an unstandardized coefficient of .460, a t-value of .880, and a p-value of .000. This finding aligns with empirical studies where personalized pricing led to consumer distrust despite offering discounts.

For the third hypothesis (H₀₃), which proposed that AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO) has no significant impact on consumer behaviour, the regression output reveals an unstandardized coefficient of .160, a t-value of .303, and a significant p-value of .000. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that ADO exerts a statistically significant but practically weak influence on consumer behaviour.

The final hypothesis (H₀₄) posited that Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA) has no significant impact on consumer behaviour. This variable recorded the highest unstandardized coefficient of .650, a t-value of 1.232, and a p-value of .000, along with a strong standardized beta of .650. Given these values, the null hypothesis is rejected, and we conclude that RTPA has a strong and positive impact on consumer behaviour. This supports earlier findings in both the descriptive statistics and correlation matrix, which showed RTPA to have the highest mean and strongest correlation with consumer behaviour. The result underscores the importance of timely, transparent, and responsive pricing adjustments in shaping positive user experiences in Nigeria's telecom industry.

Based on the findings of the current study, there is a substantial degree of agreement with past empirical studies reviewed in the literature. The study found that all four AI-based pricing strategies—Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI), Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR), AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO), and Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA)—have statistically significant effects on consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector. These results align with prior studies such as Hufnagel et al. (2022), who noted that although personalized pricing can enhance engagement, it may also trigger perceptions of unfairness and reduced trust, which the current study corroborates through the negative beta coefficient for PPR. Similarly,

Original Article

Bambauer-Sachse and Young (2023) reported that dynamic pricing increases consumer confusion and negative word-of-mouth, echoing this study's finding of DPI's statistically significant yet weak practical impact. Abdulsalam et al. (2024) also observed that AI-optimized discount strategies positively influence purchasing behavior, consistent with the modest positive effect of ADO found here. Most notably, this study's identification of RTPA as the strongest positive influence on consumer behaviour mirrors Huarng and Yu (2020), who emphasized that real-time pricing strategies are well received by loyal consumers when perceived as fair and transparent. Overall, the present research confirms and extends earlier findings by contextualizing them within Nigeria's telecom sector and emphasizing the need for transparency and fairness to sustain trust and behavioural engagement

5.0 Summary of Findings

The study found that all four AI-based pricing strategies—Dynamic Pricing Implementation (DPI), Personalized Price Recommendations (PPR), AI-Driven Discount Optimization (ADO), and Real-Time Price Adjustment (RTPA)—had statistically significant impacts on consumer behaviour within Nigeria's telecommunication sector. RTPA emerged as the strongest predictor, indicating that timely and responsive price changes positively influence trust, fairness perception, and purchasing intent. PPR and DPI, although statistically significant, showed negative beta coefficients, suggesting that personalization and frequent dynamic changes may trigger concerns about fairness and transparency. ADO also significantly influenced consumer behaviour but with a weaker magnitude, implying that while AI-driven discounts affect purchasing behaviour, their effect depends on timing and targeting effectiveness. Collectively, these results suggest a strong relationship between AI pricing tools and consumer behavioural responses, moderated by trust and perceived fairness.

5.1 Conclusion

This study concludes that AI-based pricing strategies play a vital role in shaping consumer behaviour in the Nigerian telecommunication sector. While technologies like RTPA have a markedly positive effect by aligning pricing with real-time demand and enhancing user satisfaction, the less favorable perception of PPR and DPI highlights the ethical and psychological barriers tied to algorithmic transparency and fairness. Despite their innovative appeal and revenue-optimizing potential, AI pricing tools risk alienating consumers if not deployed with adequate safeguards for equity, clarity, and trust. Hence, the success of AI-based pricing in emerging markets like Nigeria depends not only on algorithmic sophistication but also on consumer-centric ethical considerations and responsible communication strategies.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings, telecom firms in Nigeria should prioritize transparency and fairness in deploying AI-based pricing models, especially in DPI and PPR systems where consumer skepticism is evident. Firms should invest in customer education and real-time notifications to explain price changes and personalized offers, thereby increasing user trust and perceived value. Given the strong positive influence of RTPA, telecom providers should leverage it to offer responsive and competitive pricing while ensuring it does not disproportionately affect vulnerable users. Regulators are also advised to establish clear ethical guidelines and disclosure standards for AI-powered pricing to protect consumer interests and bridge digital literacy gaps. Future AI pricing strategies should be localized, user-friendly, and grounded in ethical AI principles to foster trust, loyalty, and sustainable adoption in Nigeria's telecom ecosystem.

References

Original Article

- Abdulsalam, T. A., Omolaja, R. A., Tajudeen, R. B., & Abdulazeez, S. O. (2024). Efficacy of digital pricing strategies on customer buying decisions in the e-commerce industry: A PLS-SEM approach. *African Journal of Stability and Development, 16(1)*, 73–123.
- Anta Callersten, J., Bak, S., Xu, R., Kalthof, R., & Bradley, S. (2024, April 16). Overcoming retail complexity with AI-powered pricing. Boston Consulting Group.
- Bambauer-Sachse, S., & Young, A. (2023). Consumers' intentions to spread negative word of mouth about dynamic pricing for services: Role of confusion and unfairness perceptions. *Journal of Service Research, 26(4)*, 560–577.
- Benbasat, I., & Barki, H. (2007). Quo vadis TAM? *Journal of the Association for Information Systems, 8(4)*, 211–218.
- Chen, J., Zhang, Y., & Wu, Y. (2024). The impact of differential pricing subject on consumer behavior. *BMC Psychology, 12(2)*, 400-431.
- Chenavaz, R. Y., & Dimitrov, S. (2025). Artificial intelligence and dynamic pricing: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Applied Economics, 28(1)*, 246-281.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly, 13(3)*, 319–340.
- Hansen, J. M., Saridakis, G., & Benson, V. (2018). Risk, trust, and the interaction of perceived ease of use and behavioral control in predicting consumers' use of social media for transactions. *Computers in Human Behavior, 80*, 197–206.
- Keni, K. (2018). The impact of trust and perceived risk on online purchase intentions in Indonesia: The role of perceived usefulness and ease of use. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 116*, 111–120.
- Legris, P., Ingham, J., & Collerette, P. (2003). Why do people use information technology? A critical review of the technology acceptance model. *Information & Management, 40(3)*, 191–204.
- Lunceford, S. (2009). An overview of the technology acceptance model: Origins, development, and future directions. *Proceedings of the Southern Association for Information Systems Conference*, 1–10.
- Ramayah, T., & Ignatius, J. (2005). Impact of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived enjoyment on intention to shop online. *ICFAI Journal of Systems Management, 3(3)*, 36–51.
- Wang, Y., Wang, Y., & Chen, W. (2023). Investigating consumer adoption of AI-powered shopping recommendations: An empirical test of the extended TAM model. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 70*, 103–112.

Original Article

- Flipkart Commerce Cloud. (2025). *A comprehensive guide on dynamic pricing algorithm*. Flipkart Commerce Cloud.
- Huang, K. H., & Yu, T. H. K. (2020). The impact of surge pricing on customer retention. *Journal of Business Research, 120*, 175–180.
- Hufnagel, G., Schwaiger, M., & Weritz, L. (2022). Seeking the perfect price: Consumer responses to personalized price discrimination in e-commerce. *Journal of Business Research, 14(3)*, 346–365.
- Inegbedion, H., Asaleye, A., & Obadiaru, E. (2023). Competitive behaviour of major GSM firms' internet data pricing in Nigeria: A game theoretic model approach. *Heliyon, 9(1)*, e12886. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e12886>
- Intuz. (n.d.). *AI-powered dynamic pricing solutions*. Intuz.
- Kamraju, M. (2024). Algorithmic pricing and consumer vulnerability: The ethical and economic implications of AI-driven pricing models. *ASEAN Journal of Economic and Economic Education, 3(2)*, 201–208.
- Kansal, S., & Agarwal, R. (2024). AI-augmented discount optimization engines for e-commerce platforms. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals, 8(5)*, 1057–1066.
- Kopalle, P. K., Pauwels, K., Akella, L. Y., & Gangwar, M. (2023). Dynamic pricing: Definition, implications for managers, and future research directions. *Journal of Retailing, 99(3)*, 555–572. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2023.11.003>
- Marwala, T. (2025). *AI is changing the price you pay — but who's keeping it honest, and what's the particular significance for Africa*. United Nations University.
- Marwala, T. (2025, May 20). AI is changing the price you pay—but who's keeping it honest, and what's the particular significance for Africa. *United Nations University – Our World Magazine*.
- Quadrant Knowledge Solutions. (2023). *SPARK Matrix: Intelligent retail pricing & promotion optimization (IRP&PO), 2023*.
- Seele, P., Dierksmeier, C., Hofstetter, R., & Schultz, M. D. (2021). Mapping the ethicality of algorithmic pricing: A review of dynamic and personalized pricing. *Journal of Business Ethics, 170(4)*, 697–719.
- Staino, P. (2024, October 30). *Planning your Cyber Week pricing strategy? Let AI lead the way*. Salesforce Blog.
- Vomberg, A., Homburg, C., & Sarantopoulos, P. (2024). Algorithmic pricing: Effects on consumer trust and price search. *International Journal of Research in Marketing, 41(4)*, 600–617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2024.10.006>

Original Article

- Wagener, T. (2025, July 8). *Personalized discounts, public gains: The welfare case for algorithmic pricing*. Computer & Communications Industry Association.
- Wu, Z., Yang, Y., Zhao, J., & Wu, Y. (2022). The impact of algorithmic price discrimination on consumers' perceived betrayal. *Frontiers in Psychology, 13*, 825420. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.825420>
- Bellis, J., & Rodríguez Ovejero, J. M. (2020, July). *Using algorithms for mobile data pricing*. Frontier Economics.